

Synthesis of Biocompatible Mn-doped TiO₂ hollow Nanospheres

Madhusudan Kr. Mahto, Amita Pathak*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur – 721302, India

*Corresponding author Email id: ami@chem.iitkgp.ernet.in

Abstract:

Among the various inorganic nanomaterials, TiO₂ holds great promise in biomedical applications because of its biological and chemical inertness. However, the hollow TiO₂ nanostructures have not been much explored in biological studies and hence an attempt have been made to synthesize hollow nanospheres of TiO₂ and Mn-doped TiO₂ at room temperature using carbon spheres as sacrificial core templates. The morphology of the synthesized TiO₂ and Mn doped TiO₂ nanostructures were confirmed through SEM and TEM studies while their chemical composition has been ascertained by XRD and XPS studies. Thermal and XRD studies revealed that phase transformation of TiO₂ from anatase to rutile occurred at temperature as low as 550 °C, when the dopant (i.e., Mn) concentration was increased from 1 to 6 mol %. The biocompatibility studies have been carried out through MTT assay that validated their suitability for biomedical applications.

Keywords: Nanospheres; Biocompatibility; Phase transformation; Biomedical application;

References

1. A Pathak et al, Appl Nanosci 5 (2015) 901–910.